

ORIGINAL RESEARCH PAPER

Education

EMOTIONAL MATURITY AND THINKING STYLES OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS – A CORRELATION ANALYSIS

KEY WORDS: Thinking Styles, Emotional Maturity, High School Students, Correlation

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ABSTRACT This paper explains the thinking styles of high school students based on emotional maturity. The investigator used survey method of research. The tools used in this study are Emotional Maturity Scale by Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava (1991) and Thinking Style Test Battery by the investigator (2016). The investigator has randomly selected 300 high school students in Sivagiri taluk for the present study. Totally ten schools were taken for the study. The sampling techniques used are random sampling method. The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation to study the relationship between temperament and emotional maturity of high school students. From the result of correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between thinking styles and emotional maturity of high school students.

INTRODUCTION

Popular thinking identifies the term emotional maturity with emotional balance or stability but a child may have achieved emotional maturity without emotional maturity. In fact stability or balance in emotional expression is an adult achievement beyond young people. Emotional maturity is a relative term, relative to the age and stage of development of a child. It is therefore the responsibility of all those who have to deal with the education of young people to determine goals of emotional maturity for each age or stage of development and then try to help children to achieve them. Emotional maturity is not emotional control for the term control is negative in import stressing check or suppression of emotions. For some stages of growth an uninhibited expression of emotions may be very desirable, as it is characteristic of that age. One who is able to control his emotions may be still very immature as he may be burning up inside with frustrations and inhibitions. Emotional maturity must be consistent with facts of development and a particular stage of development self control is an essential characteristic of emotional maturity, but it must be kept in view that an all-round development of personality calls for not only restriction or checking of emotions but also an enjoyment or rich and full living according to one's level of development.

Thinking styles, is a study of how and why homosapiens think and could be classified as interactive and reciprocal mental self-government psychology. Its major objective is to show how different thinking styles affect learning preference and how individual abilities to learn should be recognized and respected. Thinking styles gives you very powerful techniques to help you understand yourself and others. By developing your communication skills you will be able to develop more effective working relationships. Thinking styles is ideal for use in situations at work where strong relationships are critical for success. Thinking styles can also identify cultural cognitive preferences within teams and organisations. Cognitive or thinking style is a term used in cognitive psychology to describe the way individuals think perceive and remember information. Cognitive styles differ from cognitive ability (or) level, the latter being measured by aptitude tests or so-called intelligence tests.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Emotional maturity is a process in which the personality is continuously striving for greater sense of emotional health both intra physically and intra personally. "An emotional mature person is one who is able to keep a lid on feelings. He can suffer in silence. He/she can bide his/her time in spite of present discomfort. He/she is not subject to suing in mood, he is not volatile. When he does express emotion, he/she does so with moderation, decently and in good order. Emotional maturity is the ability to bear tension and it is the ability to develop high tolerance for disagree circumstance. During the last few decades, there has been a radical change in every field on account of scientific inventions and technological

advancements. To meet the challenges and requirements of this fast in the ability to think rationally and to express their thoughts clearly. Independent thinking, careful analysis and objective assessment contribute to the success in any field. Thinking is related to the learning because knowledge of a person affects ones thinking pattern. Thinking is one of the most important aspects of one's cognitive behavior. It is universally acknowledged fact that the gifted and creatively talented individuals to the maximum. Our ideas about thinking and about different kinds of thinking come largely from two fields of enquiry, philosophy and psychology. Part of the activity of philosophy is learning how to support and justify the claims that we make. It is associated with giving reasons, weighing up pros and cons, constructing arguments, solving problems and making decisions.

The specific needs for identifying these phenomena of emotional maturity and thinking style as a natural and inevitable essential outcome of student growth and development rather than among pathological symptom. The Emotional maturity and thinking style becomes important in the behavior of individuals. As the students are the pillars of the future generations their value pattern of emotional maturity and thinking styles are vital. In view of the above the present study is designed to study the relationship between emotional maturity and thinking style is entitled as 'Thinking styles and Emotional Maturity of High School Students'.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To find out whether there is any significant relationship between thinking styles and emotional maturity of high school students

METHOD OF RESEARCH USED

The investigator used survey method of research.

POPULATION

Population means the entire mass of observation. A population is any group of individual that has one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researchers. The population may be all the individuals of a particular type or a more restricted part of that group. The population of the study consists of high school students of Sivagiri taluk in Tirunelveli district.

SAMPLE

A small portion of population selected for observations is called a sample. The investigator has randomly selected 300 high school students in Sivagiri taluk for the present study. Totally ten schools were taken for the study. The sampling techniques used are random sampling method.

TOOLS USED

i. Emotional Maturity Scale

It is a standardized tool. It was developed and standardized by

Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava (1991). It consists of 48 items. *Reliability on Emotional Maturity Scale*

Reliability applies to a measure when similar results are obtained over time and across situations. Broadly defined, reliability is the degree to which measures are free from error and therefore, yield consistent results. (Singh, 2004)

The investigator used test – retest method to establish reliability of tool. For establishment of reliability, the investigator collected the required data from a total of 30 high school students of Government boys Hr. Sec. School, Puliangudi, and Government boys Hr. Sec. School, Puliangudi. After an interval of 15 days the same tools were administered to the same set of students. The reliability coefficient of the tools were established. They are given in the following table:

Table – 1
Reliability of the tool

Sl.No.	Tool	Reliability
1.	Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS)	0.69

ii. Thinking Style Test Battery

It was validated and standardized by the investigator (2016).

STATISTICAL TECHNIQUE USED

The investigator used Pearson Product Moment Correlation to study the relationship between temperament and emotional maturity of high school students.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

H0 1: There is no significant relationship between thinking styles and emotional maturity of high school students.

Table – 2
Pearson correlation analysis showing the relationship between thinking style and emotional maturity of high school students

Correlation	Calculated value of "r"	N	Table of value "r"	Remarks At 5% level
Thinking Style and Emotional Maturity	0.8942	300	0.009	S

It is inferred from the above table that the -value (0.8942) is greater than the calculated value for df (299) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus there is significant relationship between thinking styles and emotional maturity of high school students.

FINDING AND INTERPRETATION

From the result of correlation analysis, the investigator found that there is significant relationship between thinking styles and emotional maturity of high school students. Emotionally matured students, using an enhanced awareness of their emotional states and their understanding of their own reactions to varied situations, may adjust to different thinking styles to solve problems and deal with complex classroom situations. An individual with a strong left-brained thinking style might have little awareness of their own emotions and how they are communicated to others and little awareness of the emotions of others and what they are communicating and, ultimately, difficulty managing those interactions. Taken together, this could suggest that having a strong left-brained thinking style is associated with having less emotional maturity awareness and less emotional maturity management, and ultimately, low total emotional maturity. Studying learning and thinking styles based on whole-brain theory and styles association with emotional maturity adds an important dimension to the educational and developmental procedures. This emphasis is designed to increase understanding among educationalists of social and emotional adjustment. Additionally, it adds an important focus on the relationship between brain chemistry and emotional maturity.

RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

From the result of the correlation analysis, the investigator suggested the following recommendations,

- Curriculum planning should be reconsidered, and right-hemispheric students must be allocated to specific activities for developing thinking style. Moreover, gender differences associated with emotional intelligence should be taken into account in order to design appropriate psychological programs which go with the specificity of both genders.
- The government and private high school students should be trained to use different styles of learning.
- The schools can establish counselling cell for the students. Students can share their feeling and remove their stress and strain in these cells which are major issues of early adolescence age.
- The high school students should provide responsibilities according to their capacity. It will help them built self confidence which will later make them emotionally strong.
- In the class room divergent questions may be asked, so that students can think and answer in different ways.
- Problems of specific issues can be given to the students and they can be asked to solve the problems in different ways. Students can be encouraged to record their ideas and write stories, essays, plays, dialogues and stage talk.
- Excursion and field trips can be arranged to encourage pupil's curiosity and sense observation.
- Abilities in sports, music and art should be recognised and cultivated in the schools. Children may be encouraged to play with words and interest can be created in preparing models and construction of buildings using cubes, blocks and clay.

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